

The Active Region Model (ARM) for Fingering Flow in the Vadose Zone: Mathematical Derivation for Flux Boundary Conditions

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Abstract

This note presents a rigorous derivation of the optimality-based Active Region Model (ARM) for fingering flow in the vadose zone under fixed-flux boundary conditions. ARM, also referred to as a generalized Darcy–Buckingham law, describes how soil-water flow self-organizes to maximize conductivity by partitioning the medium into active and inactive regions. The derivation demonstrates that the previously established ARM relationship between water flux and hydraulic gradient remains valid under flux boundary conditions, extending earlier work based on fixed-head conditions. The results contribute to the theoretical understanding of nonlinear flow processes and preferential flow in the vadose zone.

Key words: Fingering flow; Vadose zone hydrology; Soil physics; Critical zone

Introduction

The Darcy–Buckingham law was originally developed to describe water flow in unsaturated soils under the assumption of local equilibrium. A discussion of the local-equilibrium concept in the context of thermodynamics can be found in Glansdorff and Prigogine (1971). However, this assumption breaks down when preferential flow occurs, requiring a different theoretical framework to accurately describe the flow process. Preferential flow is primarily caused by macropores and by instability of the wetting front, also known as fingering flow. Although much research has focused on macropore-driven preferential flow, comparatively little progress has been made toward a macroscopic theory or modeling approach for fingering flow.

The optimality-based ARM was developed as a macroscopic theory for fingering flow in the vadose zone (Liu, 2011, 2017, 2022; Liu et al., 2026a, b). It divides the representative elementary volume into two distinct regions: active and inactive. The active region is characterized by fingering flow, whereas the inactive region is bypassed. The macroscopic relationship between soil-water flux and the hydraulic gradient was derived from the optimality principle: the soil-water

flow pattern self-organizes to maximize flow conductivity (Liu, 2011, 2017, 2022; Liu et al., 2026a, b). Optimality has deep roots in nonlinear thermodynamics. Unlike in the Darcy–Buckingham law, where conductivity is a function of capillary pressure or water saturation, the conductivity for fingering flow in ARM is also a power-law function of water flux. Liu (2017) referred to this development as the generalized Darcy–Buckingham law.

In previous studies (Liu, 2011, 2017, 2022; Liu et al., 2026a), the mathematical derivation of the ARM relationship was based on fixed hydraulic-head boundary conditions, whereas Liu et al. (2026a) noted that “intuitively, optimal conductivity should not depend on the specific boundary conditions used in the derivation.” This short communication supports that conclusion by demonstrating that the same ARM relationship between water flux and hydraulic gradient can be rigorously derived under fixed water-flux boundary conditions.

Mathematical Derivation

Following common practice for determining large-scale flow parameters (e.g., Gelhar, 1993), we focus on steady-state flow, because this work emphasizes fully developed fingering flow. The steady-state large-scale flow equation for a homogeneous, isotropic porous medium is

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{q} is water flux. Note that all the bold characters represent vectors in this note.

The expression for energy-expenditure rate needs to be derived for applying the optimality principle. The energy of unit weight of liquid water (or hydraulic head) in a porous medium, E , is given by

$$E = z + h \quad (2)$$

where h is the average capillary pressure head within the fingering-flow zone and z is the vertical coordinate. E is also called hydraulic head in literature.

Assume that the *form* of the Darcy–Buckingham law holds, but with a different expression for hydraulic conductivity K :

$$\mathbf{q} = -K\nabla E \quad (3)$$

Define a macroscopic state variable:

$$S_* = |\nabla E|^2 = \nabla E \cdot \nabla E \quad (4)$$

A major difference between Liu (2011, 2017, 2022) and traditional unsaturated-flow theory lies in the expression for hydraulic conductivity (K). Conventionally, K in the Darcy–Buckingham law is taken to be a function only of water saturation (or, equivalently, capillary pressure). This follows directly from the local-equilibrium assumption, which is not valid for modeling fingering flow at the large scale. Following Liu et al. (2026a), we therefore use the square of the energy gradient as an additional variable to determine the large-scale conductivity for mathematical convenience. This choice is equivalent to using the water flux, because the water flux and the energy gradient are related (Eq. (3)). Thus, the large-scale hydraulic conductivity is

$$K = K_s k_r(h, S_*) \quad (5)$$

where K_s and k_r are the saturated hydraulic conductivity and relative permeability, respectively. As indicated above, we consider the following fixed water-flux boundary condition in this derivation:

$$\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} = q_n(\mathbf{x}) \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the unit vector normal to the boundary and \mathbf{x} is the position vector along the boundary.

The magnitude of the total energy dissipation in the flow domain is then given by:

$$I_w = \iiint KS_* dV \quad (7)$$

A detailed derivation of Eq. (7) is given in Liu (2011, 2017, 2022). Note that, unlike in Liu (2011, 2017, 2022), the right-hand side of the above equation does not carry a negative sign because we consider only the magnitude here.

To apply the optimality principle, namely that under fixed water-flux boundary conditions the system self-organizes to maximize flow conductivity (or, equivalently, minimize total energy dissipation), we construct the following augmented functional by combining all constraints:

$$\mathcal{F} = \iiint [KS_* + \lambda(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}) + \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot (\mathbf{q} + K\nabla E) + \beta(S_* - |\nabla E|^2)] dV \quad (8)$$

where λ , $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, and β are Lagrange multipliers.

Taking the variation of Eq. (8) with respect to S_* :

$$\delta_{S_*} \mathcal{F} = \iiint \left(\frac{\partial(KS_*)}{\partial S_*} + \beta \right) \delta S_* dV = 0 \quad (9)$$

one obtains

$$\beta = - \frac{\partial(KS_*)}{\partial S_*} \quad (10)$$

Taking the variation of Eq. (8) with respect to \mathbf{q} gives:

$$\delta_{\mathbf{q}} \mathcal{F} = \iiint (\lambda \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{q} + \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \delta \mathbf{q}) dV = 0 \quad (11)$$

Using integration by parts and applying the divergence theorem, we obtain

$$\iiint (\lambda \nabla \cdot \delta \mathbf{q}) dV = \iint \lambda \delta \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n} dA - \iiint \nabla \lambda \cdot \delta \mathbf{q} dV \quad (12)$$

where A is the surface area on the boundary. Note that the first term on the right-hand side of the above equation is zero under fixed water-flux boundary conditions. Substituting Eq. (12) into Eq. (11) gives:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \nabla \lambda \quad (13)$$

Finally, we take the variation of Eq. (8) with respect to E . In this part of the derivation, we use the fact that K is a weak function of E , as justified by Liu et al. (2026a) for gravity-dominated unsaturated flow in soils. Thus, the dependence of K on E is neglected here.

$$\delta_E \mathcal{F} = \iiint \mathcal{M} \cdot \nabla (\delta E) dV = 0 \quad (14)$$

where

$$\mathcal{M} = K \boldsymbol{\alpha} - 2\beta \nabla E = K \nabla \lambda - 2\beta \nabla E \quad (15)$$

Integrating Eq. (14) by parts and applying the divergence theorem, we rewrite Eq. (14) as

$$\delta_E \mathcal{F} = \iint \mathcal{M} \cdot \mathbf{n} \delta E dA - \iiint (\nabla \cdot \mathcal{M}) \delta E dV = 0 \quad (16)$$

The solutions to Eq. (16) are

$$\mathcal{M} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad (17)$$

on the boundary and

$$\nabla \cdot \mathcal{M} = 0 \quad (18)$$

within the flow domain. A sufficient solution that satisfies both conditions is:

$$\mathcal{M} = K\nabla\lambda - 2\beta\nabla E = 0 \quad (19)$$

Under the condition that a unique solution exists for the optimality problem under consideration, Eq. (19) also holds as the necessary solution. This equation indicates:

$$\lambda \propto E \quad (20-1)$$

$$K \propto \beta \quad (20-2)$$

Combining Eqs. (10) and (20-2) gives

$$\frac{\partial K}{\partial \ln S_*} \propto K \quad (21)$$

The above equation is identical to that obtained from fixed hydraulic-head boundary conditions (Liu, 2011, 2017, 2022), indicating that this result does not depend on the specific boundary conditions.

As detailed in Liu et al. (2026a), the ARM relationship between water flux and hydraulic gradient can be derived from Eq. (21) as follows:

$$\mathbf{q} = -fK_s k_{r,local}(h)\nabla E \quad (22)$$

where $k_{r,local}$ is the water relative permeability in the fingering-flow zone and f is the fraction of the fingering-flow zone, given by

$$f = \left(\frac{|q|}{K_s}\right)^a \quad (23)$$

where a is the ARM parameter, which has been shown to fall within a narrow range between 0.4 and 0.5 (Liu et al., 2023, 2025; Liu, 2022).

Discussions

This note confirms the intuitive expectation of Liu et al. (2026a) that “optimal conductivity should not depend on the specific boundary conditions used in the derivation.” A rigorous mathematical derivation of the ARM relationship between water flux and hydraulic gradient is provided both in this note and in Liu et al. (2026a). This relationship is held under different boundary conditions

and mathematically consistent with the fractal characteristics of fingering-flow patterns commonly observed in practice (Liu, 2022).

ARM results have been demonstrated to be consistent with observations from laboratory and field experiments. The relationship between the fingering-flow fraction and water flux (Eq. (23)) agrees well with laboratory observations, with the ARM parameter falling within a narrow range (0.4–0.5) across different soil types (Liu et al., 2023). ARM has been shown to reliably reproduce field results from dye-infiltration experiments using only laboratory-measured soil properties, without the need for additional tunable parameters (Liu et al., 2025). As discussed in Liu et al. (2026b), ARM has also been used by other researchers to model field-scale flow and transport in the vadose zone, with ARM parameter values within the range of laboratory observations (Sheng et al., 2009; Engstrom and Liu, 2015; Chen et al., 2022).

Although the optimality principle underlying ARM is often framed within nonlinear thermodynamics, it can also be understood through an analogy with Darwinian evolution. Biological evolution is far more complex than fingering flow, yet both systems involve nonlinear processes, feedback mechanisms, and the progressive amplification of small variations. In biological systems, organisms continuously exhibit variation at multiple levels, including individuals, populations, DNA, and genes. Much of this variation arises from random mutations in genetic sequences. Depending on their effects, mutations may be harmful, neutral, or occasionally beneficial. Through natural selection, beneficial mutations are preferentially retained and propagated, whereas harmful mutations tend to be eliminated over successive generations.

A comparable process can be envisioned for water flow in the vadose zone. Natural perturbations in fluid and medium properties are present, even when they are not explicitly included in the hypothesis. Although these perturbations may be small, they provide the initial seeds from which fingering-flow patterns can emerge. In this sense, natural perturbations play a role analogous to mutations in Darwinian theory. If a perturbation produces a slight change in the flow pattern that lowers flow resistance, that change can be reinforced through positive feedback and amplified over time, leading to further reductions in resistance. This feedback-driven amplification explains the development of fingering in unsaturated flow systems; by contrast, negative feedback would tend to dampen perturbations rather than enhance them. Thus, the evolution of fingering flow toward minimum flow resistance is analogous to natural selection, in

which advantageous variations are preserved because they improve adaptation to the surrounding environment.

Concluding Remarks

This note provides a rigorous derivation of the Active Region Model (ARM) relationship for fingering flow in the vadose zone under fixed water-flux boundary conditions and demonstrates that the same conductivity relationship previously obtained for fixed hydraulic-head boundary conditions is recovered. This result supports the view that the optimal large-scale conductivity for fully developed fingering flow is an intrinsic outcome of flow self-organization rather than an artifact of a particular boundary condition. Together with prior laboratory validation, field evaluation, and related applications of the active fracture model, the present derivation strengthens ARM as a generalized Darcy–Buckingham law for nonequilibrium unsaturated flow and supports its broader use in modeling water flow and solute transport in the vadose zone.

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